

School Attitude and Academic Performance of Students from a Relocation Area in Cavite: Basis for a Planned School/Classroom Motivational Activities

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ARTICLE INFO

Keywords: School attitude, Academic performance, Pabahay students, Relocation area

Received : 5, June

Revised : 18, July

Accepted: 18, August

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ABSTRACT

This descriptive study was conducted to determine the relationship between school attitude of students from a relocation area in Cavite and their academic performance in order to devise a school/classroom motivation activity. The study was based on the concept interpreted by Godwin and Okoronka (2015) of the Congruity Theory. The questionnaire used was adopted in the SAAS- R- School Attitude Assessment Survey-Revised developed by McCoach and Siegle (2013) as the means of gathering the data. The questionnaire was composed of 35 items which were divided into 5 dimensions namely: (a) Academic Self-Perception, (b) Attitude toward Teachers and Classes, (c) Attitude toward School, (d) Goal Valuation, (e) Motivation and Self-Regulation. The respondents of the study were 122 students residing from a relocation area in Cavite, and their 15 teachers.

INTRODUCTION

Attitude is a big contributory factor to the success of students not only in the process of learning and academics but also to its holistic development. Attitude is technically abstract in nature. Attitude defined as a general and enduring positive and negative feeling about some person object or issue (Petty and Cacioppo, 2008). Attitude is the underlying way humans think, feel and act how one react to the world. It determines the quality and effectiveness of all thinking, emotions and behavior thereby, the positive or negative consequences of that behavior (Grimme and Grimme, 2000). Attitude is a positive or negative view of an "attitude object" a person, behavior or event (Burkhardt & Schoenfeld, 2003). Research has shown that people can also be "ambivalent" towards a target, meaning that simultaneously possess a positive and negative attitude towards it (dissonance) (Marsh &Yeung, 1996).

In psychological point of view attitudes are relatively stable evaluation of persons, objects, or situations on issue along continuum ranging from positive to negative (Wood et.al, 2005). The schools are often expected to establish socially approved attitudes, such as respect for other people, cooperativeness, as well as positive attitude towards knowledge and learning and attitude of self- efficacy (Wadworth et al., 2005). It is believed that attitude is an important predictor of achievement as students who have more positive attitudes toward school engage more in learning activities and persist longer in their effort to complete difficult tasks (Reyes 1984; Wilkins 2002). Given a similar scholastic aptitude, students with better strategies and positive attitudes toward learning tend to show higher academic achievement. Even with low scholastic aptitudes, but with positive attitudes toward learning, may obtain better results than those with higher aptitudes (Aluja and Blanch, 2004).

The researcher focused this study to a group of students from a government relocation project called "Pabahay". They came from different depressed areas in Metro Manila. They were enrolled in a public secondary school in which the higher percentage of the enrolees are native of the place. Most of these native dwellers come from middle class families.

The researcher is a teacher in the said school. It has been observed that these students were tagged as "Pabahay students"; although able they tend to be underachievers. A review of their previous grades lend some strength to the observation that they are underachieving.

Underachievement as defined by McCoach and Siegle (2014) is the difference between potential or ability and performance achievement. They further explained that a student who appears capable of succeeding in school but nonetheless struggling is often referred to as underachiever.

They also pointed that some of the factors commonly related to underachievement include low self-motivation, low goal valuation, and negative attitude towards school and teachers and other negative attitudes towards school.

The aforementioned situation moved the researcher and conducted this study to determine if school attitude is related to the academic performance of the relocated high school students.

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

This chapter presents related literature such as articles, abstracts, and previous studies. These were summarized from books, journals and published/unpublished, Theses and Dissertations. These were grouped into topics: (a) Motivation to Learning, (b) Students' Attitude towards Teachers and Classes, (c) Self Perception and Self Concept (d) Academic Performance of Students, (e) School Attitude Towards Learning, (f) Goal Valuation and Achievement Goals, (g) Underachievement of Students, (h) School Attitude and Academic Performance. A synthesis of these literature is presented at the end of the chapter.

Motivation to learning

Motivation is very vital to learning of students since it's something that drives them to do their job that builds knowledge (Nguyen, C. 2008). Which is also essential factor on student's character and behavior as Guay et al., 2010 stated motivation refers to "the reasons underlying behavior". Motivation is a determinant in student's learning since, students who are not willing to learn regardless of how good the instructors are will definitely will not learn, but those who do want to learn will learn. Motivation is optimized when students are exposed to a large number of these motivating experiences and variables on a regular basis. That is, students ideally should have many sources of motivation in their learning experience in each class. (Palmer, 2007; Debnath, 2005; D'Souza and Maheshwari, 2010). It involves collaboration of related beliefs, perceptions, values, interests, and actions. Intrinsic motivation is animated by personal enjoyment, interest, or pleasure, whereas extrinsic motivation is governed by reinforcement contingencies (Lai, E. 2011). Which is in contrast with students who are motivated intrinsically tend to develop high regard for learning course information without the use of external rewards or reinforcement (Senge et al., 1994 as cited by Lai, E. 2011).

The idea of intrinsic motivation is tightly related to intrinsic value. Intrinsic motivation refers to motivation that is animated by personal enjoyment interest, or pleasure, and is usually contrasted with extrinsic motivation, which is manipulated by reinforcement contingencies (Guay et.al., 2010 cited by Mahdikhani, Z., 2016). Normally, extrinsic motivation affects by the provision of rewards, which can be either tangible or intangible. However, extrinsic motivation can come about other means. Self-determination theory distinguishes various different types of regulatory mechanisms that can act as reinforcement. External regulation corresponds to the lowest level of self-determination, where behavior is motivated by a desire for reward as punishment avoidance. Introjected regulation occurs when behavior is driven

by internal pressures such as obligation or guilt. Eventually, in integrated regulation, the regulator is actually consistent with an individuals' other values and needs and becomes part of one's self-identity. This latter type of regulation is the closest to intrinsic motivation (Guay et.al.,2010).

According to Lei 2010, students who are motivated externally are at greater risk of performing lower academically than intrinsically motivated students. It is interesting to note that non- traditional students report higher levels of intrinsic motivation than traditional students (Dean and Dagostino, 2007; Daniels,2010; Bye, Pushkar, and Conway, 2007; Afzal et al., 2010).

In the study of Abdurrahman and Garbi (2014) consisted of 137, 914 junior high school students in Kebbi state out of which 383 students were sampled. Two hypotheses were tested at 5% level of significant. Results showed that gender difference were significant when impact of motivation on academic achievement was compared in male and female students. The results also indicates that there is significant difference in the academic achievement of highly motivated and lowly motivated students in mathematics.

In this study the planned school/classroom motivation activities are the end product if and when the attitude toward school needs to be reinforced.

Students Attitude Toward Teachers and Classes Mary Chamberlain (2002) said that great teacher makes a difference. They have passion that seeps through the skin- a love of learning. Great progress ('a revolution') was made but a working hum and engagement is now not enough. What are now needed are quality learning conversations between teachers and learners. It is about extending rather than supervising, about linking to the child's world, about creating lines of desires, about not seeing the curriculum as a straitjacket. The curriculum it seems is more a direction.

In the study conducted by Gottfredson et.al. (2009) the survey contained 15 questions quantifying how much students feel that teachers respect and value their contributions. The items composed how these teachers clarify questions as well as students' perceptions of the teachers' appraisal of their achievement. The survey also measured the students' academic self-perception as well as their self-appraisal of their own level of achievement and the strong beliefs in capable of meeting these academic challenges (Gottfredson, 2009).

In the findings of the study it established that students readily perceived and conformed to the low expectations meted out by the teachers.

The decreased performance and low achievement observed in these students is clearly detrimental to school attitude (Gottfredson, 2009).

Dowling, et.al. (2003) believed that human teachers characteristically perform a wide range of activities that are subsumed under the general heading of 'teaching'. Those include planning and designing, demonstrating, guiding, telling, questioning, testing, recording, motivating, and criticizing even learning. Many of these aspects of a teacher's role require significant expertise and the making of finely tuned and sensitive judgments based on both breadth and depth of experience. This is important, for instance, in relation to the provision of appropriate scaffolding to learners. It can also be argued that the

human teacher is in a strong position, in particular by virtue of overall life experience and sophistication as a communicator, to both model and facilitate co-operative learning behaviors.

According to attachment theory, relationships with supportive caregivers, characterized by trust, responsiveness, and involvement, promote social and emotional development through the development of healthy internalized working models. Children with supportive internal working models feel a sense of security that allows them to explore novel situations (Bretherton & Munholland, 1999 cited by Delvecchio, et.al. 2013).

Therefore, when teachers are warm and supportive, they provide students with a sense of connectedness with the school environment and the sense of security to explore new ideas and take risks – both fundamental to learning (Mitchell-Copeland, Denham, & DeMulder, 1997; Murray & Greenberg, 2000; Watson, 2003).

However, it is not always easy to be warm and supportive, especially when provocative student behaviors thwart the teacher's efficacy to perform his or her primary instructional role and/or the school culture promotes punitive control measures over more authoritative approaches (G. R. Mayer, 2001).

According to the Ministerial Round Table Meeting (2003), the image of the teacher as a specialist in a specific subject who stands alone in front of the class is still a reality today in many contexts, particularly at the elementary level. However, this perception of the role of teachers no longer matches the demands of teaching and the expectations that are made with regard to the education of young people.

The teaching profession is continually changing knowledge and ways to access it. The influence of the media, societal demands, and social environment the students themselves plays a major role.

This study also aimed to reveal the attitude of the respondents toward the teacher. It is therefore necessary to know how teachers could deal in situation where attitude of students toward teachers need to be improved.

Self-Perception/ Self-Concept

Self-concept is the perception that individuals have of their own worth. This includes a composite of their feelings, a generalized view of their social acceptance, and their personal feelings about themselves (Bellmore & Cillessen, 2006). According to Walz (1991) as cited by Sternke (2010) high self-esteem as appreciating oneself and acknowledging self-worth, self-control, and competence, with a corresponding positive attitude and high self-evaluation.

Self-concept is one of the areas that Thomas (2015) has associated with attitude toward learning. But in this study it is identified as self-perception. Using GPA as measure of achievement, Thomas has found that indirectly motivation and positive attitudes about mathematical ability tend to be linked to achievement through participation in academic activities.

Same through with the statement mentioned by Rocco (2005) that motivation and self-regulation were shown to affect learning. Recent research in post-secondary education has emphasized factors such as motivation, self-regulation, collaboration and procrastination.

Zimmerman (2008), views self-regulated learning as “proactive processes that student use to acquire academic skill, such as setting goals selecting and deploying strategies, and self-monitoring one’s effectiveness. Sustained self-regulation of learning is related to students’ motivational feelings and beliefs. Self-regulated students are generally more motivated and higher achievers (Bembenutty & White, 2009; Bempechat, 2004). Additionally, Hoskins and van Hoof (2005) describe students who demonstrate an “achieving orientation as strategic, organized, and competitive, able to work effectively, aware of the implication of the academic demands, and having high achievement motivation.

In England, 96 percent of secondary school pupils believe that they are “Average” or above when asked how good they are at their school work (Gibbons and Silva 2007), and predict GCSE scores 10% above their actual achievement (Sullivan, 2006). In higher education too 90%, of first year students reported being average or above average (Thorpe et al, 2007). Some of these studies also report that female and lower social class pupils under-estimate their own performance (Sullivan) and over-estimate the average performance of the group (Thorpe et al.).

Further evidence suggests that these differences in self-perception have important consequences. Marsh et al. (2005) use longitudinal data to show that students who are better at assessing themselves allocate their study time more efficiently and have better academic outcomes. Moreover, Murnane et al. (2001) show that self-esteem is associated with higher earnings. However, Baumeister et al. (2003) in their review find no causal effect of self-esteem on educational attainment. One reason for this finding may be that over confidence can have adverse as well as positive consequences when it comes to participation in risky activities.

On the other hand, self-efficacy is the belief in one’s ability to complete a task, is also important to performance. To understand deeply Bandura (1993) suggests that self-regulatory skills will not contribute much if students cannot get themselves to apply them persistently in the face of difficulties, stressors, and competing attractions. Klassen, Krawchuck, and Rajini (2008), argue that self-efficacy for self-regulation, they find that self-efficacy for self-regulation is negatively related to higher grades.

Students’ perceptions of teacher’s support have a direct effect on their interest and motivation and teachers’ expectations of student achievement (which has an effective component) influence the way they behave toward their students and thus can affect students’ motivation, self-perceptions, and academic performance (Jussim & Harber, 2005).

In this study the three areas of attitude toward school revealed self-perception of the respondent students. The articles reviewed help very much in understanding what self-concept of students is.

Academic Performance of Students

Academic performance is a complex student behavior and underlies several abilities, e.g., memory, previous knowledge or aptitude as well as psychological factors such as motivation, interests, temperaments or emotions, to name a few (Deary, Whiteman, Starr, Whalley, and Fox, 2004).

Educational psychologists and researchers have argued that there are many determinants of academic performance, one of them being academic behavior (Chamorro-Permuzic and Furnham, 2003).

Noble (2006), students' academic accomplishments, and activities, perceptions of their coping strategies and positive attributions, and background characteristics like family income, parent's level of education, guidance from parents and number of negative situations in the home were indirectly related to their composite scores, through academic achievement in high school. The students face a lot of problems in developing positive study attitudes and study habits. Guidance is of the factor through which a student can improve study attitude and study habit and is directly proportional to academic achievement. The students who are properly guided by their parents have performed well in school. Guidance from the teacher also affects students' performance. The guidance from parents and teachers affect the performance of the students (Hussain, 2006).

Moreover, socio-economic factors like attendance in class, family income, and parents' educational attainment, teacher-student ratio, presence of trained teacher in school, sex of students and distance of school can also affect the performance of the students (Raychauduri et.al., 2010). In addition, Kernan, Bogart and Wheat (2011) academic success of graduate students will be enhanced if the optimal health related barrier are low.

Raychauduri et.al., (2010) reiterated that numerous studies have been done to identify those factors which are affecting students' academic performance. But in contrast to Raychauduri statement, Hijaz and Naqvi (2006) observed that there is negative relationship between the family income and students' performance. Transversely, some researchers, for instance, Robinson and Jackson, share the opinion that apparent relationship exists between attitude and academic achievement. Ducttle and Wolk also maintain little correlation exists between students' attitude and classroom performance.

They claimed that factor like intelligence, locus of control, environment and grade level affect performance apart from attitude. Harb and El-Shaarawi (2006) found that the most important factor with positive effect on students' performance is Parental Involvement.

Furthermore, parents' positive attitude towards child's education is important in determining school attendance and academic achievement of the child. Favorable attitude towards schooling and education enhances parental involvement in children's present and future studies.

Often, the affluent parent will have access to educational resources for his/her child directly or indirectly. . It is more likely that these parents will have higher regards for education, set educational goals for the child and/or be models. Also, it is more likely a child with doctors as parents will end up pursuing higher education- possibly medical school, than the child whose parent's education stopped at a high school diploma. This is not to say that the child's education is predetermined by the parent's education; however it is merely one factor that can affect the student's desire to learn.

Faced with expanding access to secondary education, the growing heterogeneity of students, the redefinition of objectives, learning content, working methods and due to low performance of the pupils, it has always been blamed on the low of efficiency of teachers. In response to this, in the article written by Evasco (2007), he quote, "We have to look for other factors to account for the deterioration of quality instruction. It is a firm belief that the failure to address quality instruction has something to do with student's socio-economic status and our culture towards education."

The quality of student's performance remains at top priority for educator, trainers, and researchers who have long been interested in exploring variables contributing effectively for quality of performance level. These variables are inside and outside the school that affects quality of students' achievement.

These factors may be termed as student factors, family factors, school factors and teacher factors (Crosnoe et al, 2004). Generally, these factors include age, gender, geographical belongingness, ethnicity, marital status, parents' educational level, parental profession, and income. The Department of Education (2002), is taking into consideration the basic concepts and philosophies of learning vis-à-vis for the truly preparing its students for the complex and global world of work. Macalino et.al., (2005), the Philippine Journal of Education (2005) stated that quality classroom instruction largely depends on quality of teachers being indispensable character in the teaching and learning process. Teachers' teaching experience also contributes to students' performance.

Acosta (2002), attempted to discover teachers' profile, competencies and students' academic achievement in selected public schools in Bulacan. Based on her findings, she concluded that the low academic achievement of students despite the perceived high level of competency of their teachers implies that the latter have not been effective in attaining their objectives. Bernardo (2000) mentioned about the problem of learning, linked the problems of students' achievement, of teaching and poor teaching practices. He also reiterated that education in the Philippines is not designed in ways that are suited to how students and teachers can best develop their skills. Furthermore, he presumed

that poor quality of inputs to the learning process yield to poor quality inputs, which explains poor quality achievements.

In the above articles several factors which relate to student academic performance were discussed such as age, gender, geographical belongingness, ethnicity, marital status, parents' educational attainment. In this study attitude toward school were investigated if it relates in student academic performance.

School Attitude Towards Learning

According Validyaas cited by Abbas et.al. (2011) attitude as "a condition of readiness for certain type of activity". The attitudes composed by individuals may be simple or complex, it could be stable or unstable, temporary or permanent and superficial of fundamental. Judgments based upon insufficient facts are likely to yield wrong results and thereby developed biased attitudes (Abbas et al., 2011). There have been various studies investigating students' school attitude toward school/learning. The results of many of this research have reported varying results. The studies on relationship between students' attitude and the students' academic performance show a positive relationship (Mohd, Mahmood, Ismail, 2011; Bramlett & Herron, 2009; Nicolaidou & Philippou, 2003; Papanastasiou, 2000).

A study conducted by Sorge (2007), examines the attitudes of 1008 students from rural New Mexico in elementary and middle schools from ages 9 through 14. A large decrease in science attitudes between the ages of 11 and 12 years, corresponding with the move from elementary to middle school was observed. The initial consideration of possible relationships between the variables developed when results from the first year of data indicated that age was a confounding variable for measuring science attitudes.

Most of the studies produced by psychologists and teachers have attempted to identify the factors that determine the learning process and to highlight possible relations among elements related to the quality of education, the teaching strategies used in the classroom and the quality of pupils' and students' performance. Brazdau and Mihai (2011) attempted to demonstrate to what extent the level of consciousness may be a determining factor for students' academic performance. The results of their research seem to indicate that there is no significant level of correlation between the value of students' consciousness quotient and that of their intelligence quotient.

A study conducted by Riaz et.al. (2011) highlights the fact that perception and performance are dependent on the students' perception of the type of learning schools. Thus, in the case of e- learning, students accept tasks more easily and are more involve in the learning process. Nonetheless, as the authors point out, it is difficult to establish that this type of learning is actually a factor that influences the learning process for a longer period of time. On the other hand, Fabunmi (2007) it highlighted the role of the classroom factors (size, space, the relationship student classroom) in determining academic

performance. The results prove that, when these factors are considered in interaction, student performance changes significantly.

Brodie cited by Chandra and Azimmudin (2013) replicated a previous study in which students' opinions about school were compared to variables such as academic ability and gender. The findings revealed that students having a high satisfaction about school had better grades than those who had lower satisfaction about school. Same study was conducted by Greenberg, Gower, Chall, & Davidson, (2003), the results disproved the findings of other studies that showed that students from lower socio-economic areas have negative attitudes toward school and school authority figures. The result also reported that lower achieving students had favorable attitudes toward school, similar to higher achieving students, and boys had favorable attitude toward school as girls.

Furthermore, Osborn (2015), conducted a relationship study between educational levels of parents and the educational achievement, aspirations, and expectations of their children. The purpose of his study was to investigate this relationship and to elucidate Hood's findings that parental educational level was unrelated to the educational achievement of the child. It was consisted of 398 senior high school students who had completed the questionnaire. They were divided into groups according to sex and level of attainment of their parents. The major conclusion was that the students tended to achieve, aspirations and expectations consistent with the educational level of their same-sex parent.

Moreover, Jackson and Lahaderne cited by Hartley (2017) conducted a study in 1967 to examine the relationship between academic success and attitude toward school and to determine if teachers are correctly assessing students' attitudes to school.

On the other hand, according Nicolaidou and Philippou cited by Mata, et.al. (2012), negative attitudes are the results of frequent and repeated failures or problems when dealing with mathematical tasks and these negative attitudes may become relatively permanent. In addition, when children first go to school, they usually have positive attitude towards mathematics however as they progress their attitude becomes less positive and frequently become negative. Furthermore, Kogce, et.al cited Mata, et.al. (2012), he found significant differences between younger and older students' attitude towards mathematics with 8th graders having lower school attitude than 6th graders.

Teachers were surveyed using an instrument to measure their opinions about students' opinion about school based on students' academic success. The results showed that there was no significant relationship between attitude toward school and academic achievement. The result showed that there were no significant relationship between attitude toward school and academic achievement. This study also investigated the relationship of school attitude towards learning academically.

Goal Valuation and Achievement Goals

Achievement goal theory, one of the most active motivational theories, has emerged to explain achievement behavior (Anderman, Urdan, & Roeser, 2003; Pintrich, Conley, & Kemper, 2003) as cited by Kahraman (2011). Achievement goal theory is focused on the goals of achievement tasks, not general life goals (Pintrich, Conley & Kempler, 2003). To say it clearly, the researchers of this theory are interested in what drives students to complete the tasks and why do students want to achieve the tasks (Anderman, Urdan, & Roeser, 2003; Elliot & Harackiewicz, 1996; Midgely, Kaplan & Middleton 2001; Pintrich, 2000 cited by Fadlelmula, F. 2010). The achievement goal theory was developed in the late 1970's and early 1980's (Elliot & Harackiewicz, 1996; Shih, 2005). Early researchers of this theory distinguished two achievements goals; mastery goals and performance goals. Assessing students' goal achievement allows us to gain a valuable insight into the variety of ways in which students engage, evaluate and perform within the educational system (Roebken, 2007 cited by Rendall, et.al., 2009). For instance, academic outcome (goal achievement) is suggested to be affected by students' beliefs. Their beliefs about ability, effort, and goal setting, and task difficulty can potentially play an important role in determining their overall academic performance (Elliot & McGergor, 2002; McCollum, 2005; Weiner, 1985 cited by Rendall, et.al., 2009).

Mastery goals are concerned with learning and understanding a task and improving competence skills, while performance goals focus on demonstrating competence or ability (Elliot & Harackiewicz, 1996; Church & Elliot, 1997; Pintrich, 2000; Linnenbrink & Pintrich, 2002; Pintrich & Conley & Kemper, 2003; cited by Shih, 2005).

The evolution of idea on values has been the subject on various researches. This idea primarily has been discussed and studied from the perspective of expectancy-value theory (Eccles et al., 1983; Higgins, 2007; Pekrun 2006; Rose and Sherman, 2007; Weiner 1992; Weigfield and Eccles, 1992). As defined by Lewin value or valence of an activity with respect to its importance to the individuals. According to Higgins (2007) value both in terms of the relative worth of commodity, activity, or person and also as the psychological experienced of being attracted to an object or activity.

Valuing something means wishing to attain it but for Higgins value is a motivational force and not just a belief. Atkinson and Atkinson as cited by Wigfield (2010) formulated expectancy value model of achievement motivation to explain different kinds of achievement related behavior, such as striving for success, choice among achievement tasks, and persistence.

As stated by Elliot and Murayama (2008) cited by Phan (2013) goal is conceptualized as an aim that one is committed to that serves as guide for future behavior.

One orientation, called learning, task involvement, or mastery goal orientation means that the child is focused on improving their skills, mastering

materials, and learning new things. Another is goal orientation is performance or ego orientation meaning the child focuses on maximizing favorable evaluation of their competence and minimizing negative evaluations of competence.

The study of Wilson (2012) comparing the spelling scores of two 4th grade classes of students with various learning needs. One class, CL-1, set and monitored their achievement toward an end of quarter class spelling goal; the other class, CL-2, did not set a goal. The findings indicate that there is a significant difference in student achievement based on goal setting. It was determined that there is a significant difference in student achievement based on goal setting.

Goal setting or goal valuation was one area of attitude toward school which were investigated in this study. Its relation to academic performance of students were investigated.

Underachievement of students

The academic performance and underachievement of students have been a general issue in the field of academe. As Siegle (2012) explained: "Underachievement is the most frustrating and bewildering education issues parents and educators face" (p. 1).

According to Barbara (2005) the process of defining underachievement, identifying gifted underachievement students, explaining underachievement, and suggesting appropriate intervention remain controversial issue.

Sousa (2002) mentioned that both home and school can cause underachievement. In spite of much research to underachievement, providing lasting solutions was still a problem particularly in secondary high school. Underachievement can occur at any level of intellectual ability (Karaduman, 2013). Hollingworth's pioneering longitudinal study as mentioned by Karaduman (2013) into giftedness identified that many highly gifted students were not always permitted full use of their abilities in school, for originating new thoughts, new inventions, new patterns, and solving problems. Landis and Renchly (2013) reported on the alarming and ongoing nature of underachieving of gifted students disengagement in schools and consequential dropout rates. Thus, some research support (Davis, Rimm, & Siegle, 2011; Hoover Schultz, 2005; Weiss, 1972) the assertion that within educational context a significant proportion of those identified as gifted do not achieve according to their potential: they underachieve. Furthermore, in the words of Ritchotte, Mathews and Flowers (2014), Gifted underachievement represents a frustrating loss of potential for society. On the other hand, divergences of opinion among commentators on what constitute underachievement appear to be one of the major reasons for disagreement, and different researchers may use different measures to determine underachiever.

For example, Gallagher (1985) pointed out the danger of using intelligence tests for some gifted students who are labeled underachievers because of poor academic performance. This is because less is known about their intellectual functioning. Reis and McCoach (2000) culture on academic

performance should not be ignored when considering underachievement in schools, especially for foreigners. They maintain that these students face barriers to achievement, such as language problems.

Consequently, according to *Motivating Your Underachieving-Teenager.com* (2012), academically, underachievers commonly fail to prioritize effectively, often focusing on activities that have little long-term value while ignoring valuable experiences necessary to their futures. They also show little interests in major/core subjects.

To motivate adolescents and encourage students to learn, parents are to honor different learning styles and help students discover their own unique abilities by giving them appropriate tools for successful achievement, including the following: show respect for your child's individuality, set small, attainable goals at first, motivate the teen by finding creative ways to approach academics, give positive feedback for performance and constructive criticism to help motivate them further, create positive opportunities to improve achievement by being spontaneous and creative, find ways to stimulate a gifted but bored child, have siblings cooperate in supporting each other in studying and doing homework, find out what interests your child and work from there, and lastly allow them to investigate and discover his or her interests (AUT,2011).

Furthermore, family, school, friends, personality, everything and everyone may play a role in academics and sometimes can be influenced by the following factors: physical and long-term illness: if the students miss school for a specific amount of time, he she may fall behind with his or her studies. When the students return, there may be lack of energy and concentration and if a long-term illness persists, serious academic consequences follow (Mandel & Marcus cited by Voegeli, 2008). Poor nutrition also contributes to underachievement. A study has shown the benefits of having breakfast gives the student the ability to think clearly. Emotional factors conflict with family, friends and sibling or teachers can contribute to underachievement as well. Mental or emotional factors and learning disabilities also contribute to underachievement and affect learning (Mandel & Marcus cited by Voegeli, 2008). Intelligence contributes to a person's grade point average and academic ability, but family, school, friends, cultural, and personality have a greater influence on student's potential. All underachievers take different journeys involving lack of motivation. When reacting major problems within their family, responding to difficulties with peers, and conflicts with-one-self all respond differently. This may help gain understanding to why students underachieve academically (Wentzel as cited by Voegli, 2008). Lastly, Teacher factor is the most recommended factors impacting students learning. Accumulated evidences suggest that it moderates the effect of other risk factors like parents educational level of attainments, gender of students, socio-cultural and socio-economic backgrounds (Darling-Hammond, 2000; Pianta, Belsky,

Bendergrift, Houts, & Morrison, 2008; Rowe, 2003) as cited by (Cave & Brown, 2010).

The observed underachievement of the students from a relocation area in Cavite motivated this researcher to conduct the study. Many factors related to students' underachievement were discussed in the reviewed articles. These helped the researcher have a background knowledge on it.

School Attitude and Academic Performance

Tremendous studies have been made by various authors to vividly quantify and identify if school attitude has direct effect on the academic performance of students. Research has shown that students who like school have higher achievement and lower incidences of disciplinary problems, absenteeism, truancy, and dropping out of school (Hallinan, 2008).

Students with positive perceptions of their schools are more likely to intervene rather than ignore their peers plan to do something dangerous; and schools play an important role in creating a culture where students take responsibility for one another (Syvertsen, Flanagan, and Stout, 2009).

In the study of Thiele, et.al. (2016) students from most deprived areas performed less well than more affluent students. Asian and black students performed less well than white students. Contrasting with past research, school performance was positively associated with entry grades, students from low performing school were more likely to achieve the highest degree classifications. Additionally, independent school students perform less well than comprehensive school students at final year despite entering with higher grades.

In the research of Titsworth, Quinlan, and Mazer, (2010) they mentioned that teachers' behaviors impact students' thinking in class, and these experiences are related to various indicators of their motivation, affective, and cognitive learning.

It is clear that the student's perception of how they were treated by teachers greatly influenced their attitude toward school. The better teachers' treatment of students, the more positive students' attitude, and less negative attitude.

In contrast, the research made by Bembry, Jordan, Gomez, Anderson, & Mendro cited by Mclver, (2014), socioeconomic status largely determines students achievement, what school do does not matter very much, because in the end poor kids learn very little and rich kid learn a lot.

The results of these longitudinal studies show that teachers are an influential factor of student achievement, regardless of socioeconomic status and even school location. In other words, a student having an ineffective teacher several years in a row can be at an academic disadvantage, which affects his/her progress for years; whereas, a student with a highly effective teacher can have positive gains in academic progress for years to come. But Suan (2014), insisted that teacher factor is the most affecting factor on students' achievement.

Furthermore, motivation revealed as promising factor for students learn fully, to reduce its effect other factors like parents' educational attainment, students' age and gender, socio-cultural and socioeconomic backgrounds should use as the main course of the study. School attitude of students has been dynamically subject of researchers to greatly identify its effect on the academic performance. There are still considerable questions that should be prompted with investigations.

The aforementioned factors will be the same factors if the respondents and their location changed. At what extent or degree of positivity or negativity does students' attitude will fall.

Godwin and Okoronka (2014) conducted a study entitled "Attitude and Academic Performance of Senior Secondary School Students in Physics in Nigeria, guided by the Congruity Theory. Ratings on students' Physics Attitude Questionnaire and Students' Physics Performance Test of senior secondary three students were correlated.

Difference in attitude and academic performance were tested also. They found the male students higher in academic performance. Male and female students has the same attitude towards Physics. It was also found that attitude had significant positive correlation with academic performed in Physics.

In addition, Michelli (2013) conducted a study on the relationship between attitudes and achievement in Mathematics among fifth grade students.

Different traits such as extroversion, conscientiousness, self-control and intellectual efficiency were also studied. Gender was also included as variable. She found that there is significant relationship between attitude toward and achievement in Mathematics. The male students had more positive attitude toward Mathematics. Extroversion was the only trait to have significant relationship with achievement.

Furthermore, Owoeye and Agbaje (2016) conducted a study entitled "Students Attitudes and Gender as Correlates of Students' Academic Performance in Biology in Senior Secondary School (SSS III). Involved in the study were 180 senior high school Biology students. Interest in Biology was also included as variable in their study. They found that there is significant relationship between students' attitude in Biology and academic performance in Biology. There is also significant relationship between students' interest in Biology and academic performance in Biology.

The aim of this study was to investigate the relationship of school attitude toward school of students to their academic performance. The reviewed articles on the relationship of attitude toward school to specific courses or subjects provided rich information on the variables investigated.

IMPLEMENTATION AND METHODS

This presents the research procedures used in the study. These are presented as follows: (a) research design, (b) population and respondents of the study, (c) research instruments, (d) validation and test of reliability of the instruments, (e) data gathering procedures, and (f) statistical treatment of data.

Research Design

In this study the descriptive-correlation research design was used. The descriptive-correlation method attempts to determine the extent of relationship between two or more variables using statistical data; the relationships between and among a number of facts are sought, described and interpreted (key elements of a Research Proposal- Quantitative Design, retrieved January 15, 2017 @ <https://www.bcps.org>)

Frankel (2010) went further on descriptive-correlation research method with his discussion by saying that this research method describes the degree to which two or more quantitative variables are related, and it does so by the use of a correlation coefficient.

This study described the relationship of school attitude to the academic performance of the high school students from a relocation area and now enrolled in a public secondary school.

Sequential Explanatory Method by Creswell, (2003) was also used in this study. This is a method characterized by collection and analysis of quantitative data followed by an analysis of qualitative data. Teachers of the respondent students were interviewed to get their suggestions on what motivational activities can be used in the classroom to enhance the positive school attitude of these students.

The demographic profile of the students was gathered through documentary analysis. School Form 1 (SF1) was among the documents analyzed.

Population and Respondents of the Study

The study involved a total of 122 high school students from a relocation area in Cavite. They were currently enrolled in all the grade levels in a public national high school. 15 teachers who handled them were also be involved. The list of respondents is shown in Table 1.

A total of 122 high school students composed of 47 grade 7 students, 44 grade 8 students, and 31 grade 9 students. Among the teachers, 5 are teaching in grade 7 level; 5 were teaching in grade 8 level; and 5 were teachers in grade 9.

Research Instrument

This study used the instrument developed by McCoach and Siegle (2014) the School Attitude Assessment Survey-Revised, SAAS-R.

This SAAS-R is described by the authors as psychometrically sound instrument to measure adolescents' attitudes toward school, attitudes toward teachers, goal valuation, motivation, and general academic self-perception that could be used to explore the underachievement of academically able secondary

school students. Permission to use this questionnaire was sought from the authors through email who gave their approval (Please see Appendix B.)

The SAAS-R is composed of 35 questions each of which being an indicator of one of the five factors.

These five factors are: (a) Academic Self- Perception, (b) Attitude towards Teachers and Classes, (c) Attitude towards School, (d) Goal Valuation and (e) Motivation and Self- Regulation. The authors conducted a construct validity, criterion-related validity and internal consistency reliability using close to two thousand samples from four states of America. From the pilot version they validated they found enough evidences of adequacy of such validation process and came up with the final revised version validation which exhibited reasonable fit.

The two other data gathering instruments were the interview guides which were used in asking for suggestions from the teachers for the development of more high school attitude of the students.

Documentary analysis was used in gathering the academic performance of the respondents. The grade point average of the final grades of all the respondent students were requested from the school registrar for statistical analysis.

Validation and Test of Reliability of the Instrument

The SAAS-R is a validated data gathering instrument. Validation was conducted by McCoach and Siegle, the authors.

Data Gathering Procedures

1. In the data gathering, the following procedures were undertaken:
Permission letter to use SAAS-R was sent to the two authors, McCoach and Seigle through email.
2. With the approved letter of request from the school principal to conduct the study, this researcher humbly coordinated with the school registrar to access the documents containing the academic performance of the student respondents.
3. With the approved letter of request from parents to allow their children to be involved in the study, the questionnaire was administered to the student respondents;
4. The fifteen teachers of the student respondents were interviewed;

Statistical Analysis of the Data

The following statistical tests was used in the analysis of the data gathered.

Frequency Count and Relative Frequency in Percent

Percent. These two descriptive statistics was used in discussing the demographic profile of the student respondents in terms of age, gender, year level, family income and parents' educational attainment.

Mean. This descriptive statistic was used to determine the school attitude of and academic performance of the student respondents.

t-test and F- test or one-way ANOVA. The two tests of difference were used in the comparisons of school attitude according to the demographic profile of the student respondents.

Pearson Product Moment Correlation. This correlation test was used in determining the relationship of school attitude to academic performance.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

After the data collection and analysis, data on reading abilities of the first-grade students at SDN Ngolo were obtained. The data is presented as follows:

Table 3. Result

Student	Score					Average (Final Score)
	Aspect 1	Aspect 2	Aspect 3	Aspect 4	Aspect 5	
AT	76	80	76	20	60	62,4
BD	100	100	88	60	60	81,6
BL	80	84	68	60	80	74,4
FR	84	76	60	40	40	60
LO	92	96	80	60	60	77,6
MA	84	88	72	40	60	68,8
MF	36	24	12	0	60	26,4
MH	88	92	64	40	60	68,8
PR	52	44	36	0	20	30,4
RA	44	20	16	0	40	24
RR	64	48	32	20	40	40,8
SP	100	100	92	60	80	86,4
UR	40	36	8	0	40	24,8
YD	44	24	12	0	40	24
Mean	70,2857	65,1428	51,2428	28,5714	52,8571	53,6

Explanation:

Aspect 1: recognizing letters

Aspect 2: reading meaningful words

Aspect 3: reading words without meaning

Aspect 4: fluency in reading aloud and reading comprehension

Aspect 5: listening comprehension

Diagram 1. Result

Based on the result above, it can be observed that the ability to recognize letters has an average score of 70.2857, falling within the category of "sufficient." The ability to read meaningful words has an average score of 65.1428, also categorized as "sufficient." The ability to read words without meaning has an average score of 51.2428, which falls into the "poor" category. The ability to read aloud and comprehend passages has an average score of 28.5751, categorized as "very poor." The ability to listen has an average score of 52.851, categorized as "poor."

If the average scores of the five aspects for each student are calculated, it results in the overall reading ability of the students based on the EGRA instrument test. From the table and diagram above, it can be observed that out of 14 students, 1 student falls into the "excellent" category, 3 students fall into the "good" category, 4 students fall into the "sufficient" category, 0 students fall into the "poor" category, and 6 students fall into the "very poor" category. The overall average score, when calculated, indicates that the general reading ability of the students at SDN Ngolo is 53.6. Therefore, it can be concluded that the reading ability of first-grade students at SDN Ngolo is poor.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The reading ability of first-grade students at SDN Ngolo is poor with a score of 53.6. Out of the 14 first-grade students assessed for their reading abilities, 1 student falls into the "excellent" category, 3 students fall into the "good" category, 4 students

fall into the "sufficient" category, 0 students fall into the "poor" category, and 6 students fall into the "very poor" category. The most dominant reading ability possessed by first-grade students at SDN Ngolo is the ability to recognize letters, scoring 70.2857 in the "sufficient" category. On the other hand, the lowest reading ability among the students is the ability to read aloud and comprehend passages, scoring 28.5714 in the "very poor" category.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

We extend our heartfelt gratitude to all those who have contributed to the successful completion of this research study titled "An Analysis of Indonesian Young Learners' Reading Ability in Remote Area."

First and foremost, we would like to express our sincere appreciation to our academic advisors and mentors for their guidance, support, and valuable insights throughout the research process. Their expertise and dedication have significantly shaped the direction and quality of this study.

We are also deeply thankful to the school administration, teachers, and staff members of SDN Ngolo for their cooperation and assistance in facilitating the data collection process. Their enthusiasm and commitment to education have been crucial in ensuring the smooth progress of this research.

Furthermore, our heartfelt thanks go to the students who willingly participated in the study. Their cooperation and willingness to be part of this research have provided valuable insights into the reading abilities of Indonesian young learners in remote areas.

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